

Streak

*Social Media Promotional Application

1st Hoots

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Abstract—This project aims to create a social media promotional tool that can be utilized by a organization or individual.

Index Terms—component, formatting, style, styling, insert

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the main issues social media-driven organizations face when scaling their business is handling and organizing social media promotions and orders.

This project aims to solve this issue by allowing members to place their orders and aims to give them the tools to track and plan out their orders.

This application gives any user the ability to place, track, and control social media promotions and aims to give users the tools needed to control the focus and tempo of their campaigns.

Core App Workflow:

- register
- login
- add funds to account using payment gateway
- select a service
- add link to process order
- complete order using selected service
- staff back-end dashboard that allows users to receive special roles and discounts depending on how much they spend
- access to a dashboard that allows the user access to the appropriate information

II. AUDIENCE DESCRIPTION

A. A brief overview of our intended audience

Our intended audiences are individuals and organizations that need a commanding online presence. We offer to give them access to the resources to create campaigns where they can fine-tune their campaign focus while also being able to control the return rate of their campaign results through scheduling.

Identify applicable funding agency here. If none, delete this.

III. USER INTERVIEWS AND ANALYSIS

During the development of this project, we were able to meet the demands of the organizations that contributed to its development, as well as the individuals who were willing to help test out its public utility.

We had two organizations take part in the development.

The first organization was the primary angel investor of the project, while the second organization paid for the graphics to represent their discord server for promotional purposes.

The investment organization recommended both individual users.

A. List of Users

Client list:

- 1) Organization: oSo
- 2) Discord: Streak
- 3) Musician: Chris AM
- 4) Twitch Streamer: Vainyz

B. interviews

1) *Interview 1:* Organization representative (27, male, maintains client relations)

A user first gathers a list of promotional materials that require social media promotion, then proceeds to process them using the mass order function based on the predetermined amounts generated using the company's expected analytical model which is based on the predetermined amount.

2) *Interview 2:* Discord Server Owner (18, female, manages active discord server with) In their discord server, the user has a section in which they receive orders from their clients. In this way, staff can be allowed to sign up for the website and process orders either individually or using the website's bulk order functionality in order to make use of the website effectively.

3) *Interview 3:* Musician (22, male, independent artist) I think that users need to be able to manage and track orders within the system, as well as having access to financial information that will allow them to plan and budget appropriately and make informed decisions.

4) *Interview 4: Online Content Creator (24, male, Twitch Streamer)* The user should be able to push viewers in order to help promote themselves through the ranks of the Twitch platform in order to become a top streamer.

C. User Requirements

1) Interview 1 User Requirements:

- Ability to process mass orders for multiple social media posts at the same time
- Has the ability to process payments in order to add funds to the users account
- There is a possibility for the user to customize their campaign in order to adjust the intensity of the focus and the amount of results they receive

2) Interview 2 User Requirements:

- Allows users to register themselves by submitting an email address and password
- The ability to process orders on an individual basis
- Be able to handle bulk orders and process them in a timely manner
- Having the capability of processing payments on a regular basis
- The user can tailor their campaign to change the theme, the purpose and even how many results they would like to receive

3) Interview 3 User Requirements:

- There is a need for the user to have access to the order history of the item
- The user needs access to a funds dashboard in order to process new fund deposits and deposit history

4) Interview 4 User Requirements:

- Having the ability to process individual orders as they come in
- The user of the campaign has the option of customizing their campaign in order to change both its focus as well as the results that they receive.

D. User Requirement Validation

E. User Discussions

1) *Interview 1: Organization representative (27, male, maintains client relations)*

There should be a better description of the services on the list. It was requested that examples of what to be submitted be provided. Inquired as to whether it would be possible to add a payment processor that could accept crypto currencies as payment methods.

2) *Interview 2: Discord Server Owner (18, female, manages active discord server with)* Requested that staff be assigned to request user account reports so that people can be accurate about their earnings from their accounts. Inquired whether users could get discounts if they registered using a certain web-domain when they registered for an account. In the case

of a group of users that fall under the same organization, they could all be assigned a special website role.

3) *Interview 3: Musician (22, male, independent artist)* Because of the constant change in the way music platforms operate, there could be a greater variety of services offered to suit the current and future needs of music platforms. Is it possible to implement packages for products that are often ordered together, so as to speed up the process of placing an order by combining similar products together.

4) *Interview 4: Musician (24, male, Twitch Streamer)* It has been requested that an order updater that allows users to track their orders in real-time be added to the site.

Changes to the current working iteration of the website and companion app reflects all of these User Requirements. On both the front end and back end.

IV. LOW FIDELITY PROTOTYPES

A. Low Fidelity Descriptions

The desktop website design lends itself to be usable for both desktop usage and mobile usage. This allows a basic model vision to be obtainable utilizing the proper framework and programming tactics.

Fig. 1. Mock Up of low fidelity models

V. DIGITAL PROTOTYPING VERSUS IMPLEMENTATION

A. Desktop to mobile architecture

To implement this prototype, we utilized the Laravel framework, which consists primarily of .json, .php, and .js files.

With the help of this framework, we will be able to deploy a website that can be adapted to any mobile device so that we can develop the companion application for it.

By leveraging the flexibility of the Laravel framework and the techniques of developing mobile apps for our websites, we can produce a two-for-one site. As long as the design and implementation of the web application are properly considered, it will be possible to port a desktop site that performs well into a web application with excellent performance.

Below you will find a screenshot of how the website looks like on a desktop computer versus how it looks on a mobile

design. We are able to see this concept in action by looking at the section selector's "New Order" and "Bulk Order". Careful consideration in the look of the objects themselves and a pleasant roundish design is used to make it appealing to both widescreen displays and portrait displays.

Fig. 2. Desktop Implementation

Further more, some elements will get moved around when switching devices. One of these areas for improvement is that tables can either cut off in awkward places, not fully displaying information, or render improperly dropping information that is too far to the right of the table.

Fig. 3. Mobile Implementation

B. Prototypes versus Implementation

The next section will serve as a showcase of low fidelity models and their implementations.

Fig. 4. Home Page

Fig. 5. Service Listing Page

Fig. 6. Hamburger Menu Page

Fig. 7. Login Page

Fig. 8. Order Page

Fig. 9. Fund Deposit Page

VI. IMPROVEMENTS

A. Audience Reach

One issue that appeared was that if users were unfamiliar with how sites like this operated, they could find the process needing clarification or recovery. A tutorial page on the website would be a great inclusion to help the website's ease of use and reachability.

B. User Requirements

The implementation of the blog section and the news section still needs to be completed, as well as changing some of the page names and terminology used to meet a more general need. An additional payment processor that can handle crypto currencies needs to be added. A wider list of supported sites, with more options for each service to promote a healthy competitive marketplace environment.

C. Implementation issues

The rendering of certain elements needs to be improved and tested to see if there is an upper limit of service titles and descriptions—the need for foreign language support and testing to see if nonlatin alpha-numeric characters are supported.

VII. HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

A. Disk Storage Space Required

301.69 mbs

B. Physical Machine

- 2 CPU Cores
- 4 GB RAM
- 100 GB NVMe SSD Storage
- 1 GB speed internet

C. Hosting service

Hostinger.com

D. Total Cost of operation (Monthly)

The below table shows the total cost of operations per month:

TABLE I
COST OF OPERATIONS

Service	Cost
Website Hosting	16.99
Domain Cost	9.99
SSL & Firewall	5.99
Total	32.00